

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleliv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 3, DECEMBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

Nkeyemudim Emmanuel Essien
& Frank O. Udukeke

Teachers' Professionalism and their Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Akwa Ibom State

¹Nkeyemudim Emmanuel Essien, PhD; ²Frank O. Udukeke, PhD

Department of Business Education, Faculty of Vocational Education,
Library and Information Science, University of Uyo, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State

Abstract

This study determines the influence of teachers' professionalism on their job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State. The survey design was adopted for this study. Three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. The null hypotheses were formulated and tested at .05 level of significance. The population of the study comprised 7017 teachers in all the 256 public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State. The sample comprised 382 teachers drawn from the total population. The research instrument, 'Teachers Professionalism Questionnaire' (TPQ) was used for data collection for the study. The questionnaire was face-validated by three experts in the Faculty of Education, University of Uyo. Cronbach Alpha technique was used in determining the reliability of the instrument and this yielded a reliability coefficient of .95. Mean and standard deviation were used in answering the three research questions, while the t-test statistics was used in testing the three null hypotheses at .05 level of significance. The study revealed that code of conduct, control entry and training have a high influence on the job performance of public secondary school teachers in Akwa Ibom State. Also, the study showed teachers did not differ in their mean ratings on the influence of control entry, code of conduct and training on the job performance of public secondary school teachers in Akwa Ibom State. Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that non-adherence to professionalism indicators has made the teaching profession to be dominated by quacks who lack teaching skills, professional behaviour and knowledge required for effective job performance that could bring about desirable changes in students' academic performance. It was recommended that policymakers and unions in education should ensure that only qualified and licensed teachers are allowed to practice the profession as it is obtainable in other professions.

Keywords: Teachers, Professionalism and Job Performance

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 3, DECEMBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

*Nkeyemudim Emmanuel Essien
& Frank O. Udukeke*

Introduction

Education is pivotal in the development of any nation. The development of any nation depends to a large extent on the quality of education it provides. Great nations of the world do not toy with their educational system and by extension with the development of their teachers. The world over, sustainable development is strongly linked to the educational system. Secondary school as one of the three levels of education in Nigeria has a crucial role in preparing individuals for higher education. Specifically, the Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013) stipulated in its National Policy on Education that the objectives of the secondary school include: fostering patriotism, national unity and security with emphasis on the common ties despite the nation's diversity; raising morally upright and well-adjusted individuals who can think independently and rationally, respect the views and feelings of others and appreciate the dignity of labour, among others. For these laudable objectives to be achieved in the educational system, teachers are recruited to impart knowledge and skills to students who will in turn contribute to national development.

In professional usage, a teacher is a person (male or female) who is trained or recognised and employed to facilitate learning processes in a classroom situation to achieve set educational goals. In ordinary usage, however, the term is often used to refer to anybody who imparts knowledge or skills to someone to acquire or change some skills, attitude, knowledge, ideal or appreciation. Oleforo and Udukeke (2018) opined that a teacher creates and influences desirable changes in the behaviour of his pupils. 'A teacher is someone who has been trained professionally in a Teacher's Training College or Faculty of Education of a University or similar institution that is engaged in Teacher Education Programmes' (Ogbodo, Etuk & Afangideh, 2013). Besides, such a person must be certified to teach and is involved in teaching. Certified teachers are usually those who graduated from accredited educational programmes in Colleges and Universities. At the secondary school level, a teacher may possess one or more of the following educational qualifications: National Certificate in Education (NCE), Bachelor's Degree in Education (B.Ed), Bachelor of Science/Art in Education (B.Sc.Ed/B.A.Ed), Master degree in Science/Arts Education (M.Sc.Ed/M.A.Ed) and Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Education. More so, he/she must be certified and licensed to teach by the Teachers

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Elevis Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 3, DECEMBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

*Nkeyemudim Emmanuel Essien
& Frank O. Udukeke*

Registration Council of Nigeria (TRCN). After the formal training, a teacher ought to possess adequate instructional delivery capacity which could help him to perform his job as expected.

Job performance refers to the input of a teacher towards the achievement of the school goals. It reveals teachers' strengths, weaknesses and how well they have done their job. Teachers' performance is often measured through students' performance. A teacher is said to have performed well if the students taught can demonstrate the behavioural capabilities stated at the beginning of a particular lesson (Ogbodo, Etuk & Afangide, 2013). Emah and Etuk (2013) argued that learning is an important criterion of successful teaching. Job performance in the teaching profession brings about a relative performance change in a learner's behaviour. But where this is not evident, the teaching processes have to be well-examined for possible improvement. Job performance in teaching contributes to a student's understanding, improves his abilities and skills and develops in him more desirable attitudes. The number of years a teacher spends in the school system could also affect his/her performance capability. This is so because the teacher has learning opportunities with the school. He/she could learn from colleagues and the process of job performance itself. To ensure effective performance, a teacher must adhere to the tenets of the teaching profession.

A profession is an occupation requiring special education, such as law, medicine, engineering or teaching from which a person earns a living. According to Hornsby (2010), 'a profession is a paid occupation especially one that requires advanced education and training'. Tedjere (2008) saw a professional as someone who has gone through a period of educational training and is experienced and capable of offering a well-informed opinion on the solution to human problem, change of human condition, provision of a need or fulfillment of aspiration or development of any idea or matter. A professional must be competent in his vocation. Competence is nurtured first by education, through training which included lectures, reading and practical work.

Professionalism represents the effort of a vocation to gain full control over its work and enhance its social and economic position in society. Generally, a profession comes into being as people who practice an occupation requiring skills, work out a common basis for training, interest and standards. The teaching profession has some

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 3, DECEMBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

*Nkeyemudim Emmanuel Essien
& Frank O. Udukeke*

characteristics that protect the profession. It is common to assume that teaching is what anybody can do, but this is not true, because before one can teach effectively, he must be schooled.

The teacher is the hub of the educational system because the school cannot be better than its teachers. The teachers constitute the most vital factor in the education system because it is upon the number, quality and devotion to duty that the effectiveness of any educational system depends. Ditimiya (2008) opined that a teacher guides learning by motivating the learner or by arousing his desire to learn. By stimulating the learner and allowing him to ask questions, the teacher helps the student to establish the act and science of teaching. Teaching is, therefore, more than telling or testing. It is a complex art of guiding individuals through a variety of selected experiences to bring about worthwhile changes in behaviour. Tedjere (2008), Ogbodo, Etuk and Afangideh (2013) agreed that teaching as a profession has some distinct characteristics. These include: control entry, training and code of conduct.

Entry into a profession is guided by setting and enforcing standards for selection, training, license and certification (Jekayinfa, 2013). Igwegbuike and Ekwejuno-Etchie (2008) contended that 'the admission of members into a profession is usually controlled to ensure that only those who are qualified and fit are allowed to practice'. For example, the Nigerian Medical Association (N.M.A.) controls the admission of new medical doctors into the profession. In a similar vein, every legal practitioner is adequately schooled in a recognized institution, proceeds to Law School and thereafter is attached to a recognized legal chamber where he can be registered as a legal practitioner and becomes a member of the Nigerian Bar Association (NBA).

However, the Nigerian teaching service has no control over its entry. Anybody and everybody can be a teacher. In fact, people who have searched for jobs in their areas of specialisation and failed, go into teaching until they find their choice jobs. The minimum qualification for entry and practice are not being strictly adhered to as graduates without teaching qualifications are recruited, especially at the secondary school level. In many professions, an aspirant must possess additional professional qualifications to qualify for practice. For example, doctors undergo internship for a year, acquiring practical skills before they are qualified to practice. It is the same for lawyers

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Elektiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 3, DECEMBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

*Nkeyemudim Emmanuel Essien
& Frank O. Udukeke*

and engineers. This is in addition to their university degrees (NOUN, 2014). However, the Nigerian Union of Teachers does not control the entry and exit of its members as recruitment into the educational system are controlled by politicians.

A code of conduct of a profession constitutes the main yardstick for measuring the practitioner's standards of behaviour required in a specific profession. Tedgere (2008) explained that codes of conduct are set of rules, guidelines or principles which spell out inter and intra-group conduct. The code of conduct covers issues relating to personal relationships with other members of the profession, clients, employers and other stakeholders. It also protects ignorant clients from being manipulated to fulfil personal gains. It ensures uniformity, high standard and continued enhancement of reputation. A well-articulated and executed code of ethics assures the public of the standard of service they are most likely to expect when transacting business with members of a certain profession or organisation. Salahudina, Alwia, Siti Baharuddina and Halimata (2016) investigated the relationship between work ethics and job performance. The study found that work ethics and job performance are positively and significantly related.

Just as tangible assets such as plants, machines and motor vehicles depreciate (reduce in value) due to wear and tear as a result of continuous usage and passage of time, so do knowledge, skills, competencies, instructional methods and material become obsolete due to changes in technology as well as societal needs. Oleforo, Udukeke and Abba (2016) explain that training supplies the skills, knowledge and attitude needed by staff in schools. According to Avery (2013), staff training is the only available tool in the human resource kit with which employers can alter the skills and knowledge level of staff to meet changing teaching methods induced by technological change, societal needs and aspirations. Peretomode and Peretomode (2011) explained that staff might become rustic if they do not update themselves with new work methods, skills and knowledge about the organisation, its work and environment.

The members of a profession have to be specially trained. They must have an optimal level of specialized knowledge. Training, according to Akpan (2004) is the exposure of staff to carefully selected learning experiences either on-the-job or off-the-job to effect positive behaviour. Dapper (2004) explained training as a short-term

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 3, DECEMBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

*Nkeyemudim Emmanuel Essien
& Frank O. Udukeke*

educational process utilizing a systematic and organised procedure by which personnel learn technical knowledge and skills for a definite purpose. Teachers are expected to acquire specialized knowledge, skills and attitudes which they utilize in instructional delivery processes. They undergo a long period of training and studying philosophy, psychology, sociology, administration, guidance and counselling, principles and practice of instructional technology and many more. Avwata (2008) maintained that teachers undergo intensive training in the Teachers Training Colleges, Colleges of Education and Faculties of Education in Universities. They acquire professional skills in the principles and practice of education. This training provides for skill acquisition and intellectual development which equip the teachers to practice as professionals in the teaching field. In fact, teacher education is well-provided for in the National Policy on Education.

A study by Rashid (2008) on the effect of manpower training and development and staff performance in the Federal College of Education (FCE), Zaria found that the various training programmes that are available in FCE, Zaria did not impact positively in enhancing the skills and knowledge of the staff, their performances on the job and service delivery. Akinyele (2017) carried out a study titled “Staff development programmes and secondary school teachers' job performance in Uyo Metropolis, Nigeria”. The findings showed that teachers who were exposed to staff development programmes such as seminars, workshops, educational conferences, symposia, among others, were more effective in their job. Jaoko, (2014) conducted a study on the relationship between academic qualification and employee performance. The finding from the study revealed that the level of training and academic qualification have a positive and significant relationship with job performance. Awan and Saeed (2014) also conducted a study on the impact of professional training on employees' performance: a case study of the Pakistani banking sector. The finding shows a positive relationship between training and employee performance.

However, it is not uncommon to see unqualified teachers doing the job of qualified teachers at all levels of education in Akwa Ibom State and Nigeria at large. Such unqualified teachers could make the achievement of education goals difficult in the state. They find it difficult to plan lessons, improvise instructional material, impart

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 3, DECEMBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

*Nkeyemudim Emmanuel Essien
& Frank O. Udukeke*

knowledge, and manage students of varied backgrounds professionally. It is upon this background the study was carried out to determine the influence of teachers' professionalism on their job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State.

Statement of the Problem

Teachers are the most important resource in any school. The strategic value of teachers stems from the fact that they combine other resources, carry out teaching activities and formulate appropriate strategies for the accomplishment of the ultimate objectives of a school – those of imparting knowledge, saleable skills and competencies to students. However, observation seems to show that many recruited teachers in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State lack the pre-requisite knowledge, professional training, competencies and skills for effective job performance.

More often than not, teachers are recruited into public secondary schools at the altar of connection, political slots, gratification and God-fatherism at the expense of merit. The teaching profession has become an all-comer's affair in recent times. As a result, teachers in many public secondary schools in the state lack deliverable capabilities to perform their job effectively. Some have challenges in lesson note preparation, instructional material improvisation, set induction, logical and coherent lesson presentation, classroom management, use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT), new teaching methods, evaluation, among others. As such, teachers seem to resort to the recycling of obsolete knowledge and skills with little or no practical value to the students and the larger society. Sadly, a handful of them often neglects their duties because they lack passion for the job.

The pertinent and unanswered question is how does teachers' professionalism influence their job performance in Public secondary schools? This provided the fertile ground for the study to be conducted to determine the influence of teachers' professionalism on job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State.

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 3, DECEMBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

*Nkeyemudim Emmanuel Essien
& Frank O. Udukeke*

Purpose of the Study

The main objective of the study was to determine the influence of teachers' professionalism on their job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State. In specific terms, the study sought to determine the influence of:

1. control entry on the job performance of public secondary school teachers in Akwa Ibom State based on gender;
2. code of conduct on the job performance of public secondary school teachers in Akwa Ibom State based on years of experience;
3. training on the job performance of public secondary school teachers in Akwa Ibom State based on qualifications.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the influence of control entry on the job performance of public secondary school teachers in Akwa Ibom State based on gender?
2. What is the influence of code of conduct on the job performance of public secondary school teachers in Akwa Ibom State based on years of experience?
3. What is the influence of training on the job performance of public secondary school teachers in Akwa Ibom State based on qualifications?

Null Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female teachers on the influence of control entry on their job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of teachers on the influence of code of conduct on their job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State based on years of service.
3. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of teachers on the influence of training on their job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State based on qualification.

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Elevis Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 3, DECEMBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

*Nkeyemudim Emmanuel Essien
& Frank O. Udukeke*

Research Method

The study was conducted in Akwa Ibom State. The descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised 7017 teachers in all the 257 public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State. The sample comprised 382 teachers drawn from the total population using the cluster sampling technique. The cluster sampling technique was adopted since the population was large. The research instrument tagged “Teachers' Professionalism Questionnaire” (TPQ) was used for data collection for the study. The instrument was designed based on the research questions that guided the study and insight from reviewed literature. The Questionnaire was divided into two sections (A and B). Section 'A' contained three items on the personal data of the respondents while B contained the items on the variable grouped in three clusters (A-C) with five items each. The questionnaire was designed on a 4-point rating scale with four response options as Very High Influence (VHI) – 4 points, High Influence (HI) – 3 points, Moderate Influence (MI) – 2 points and No Influence (NI) – 1 point. The questionnaire was face-validated by three experts in the Faculty of Education, University of Uyo. One was from the test and measurement unit and two from the Department of Business Education. Cronbach Alpha technique was used in determining the reliability of the instrument and this yielded a reliability coefficient of .95. The questionnaire was administered to the respondents by the researcher and all 380 copies of the instrument were returned. Mean and standard deviation were used in answering the three research questions. The independent t-test was used to test the three null hypotheses at .05 level of significance. The influence of teachers' professionalism on their job performance was determined using the real limit of numbers as follows: Very High Influence (VHI) - 3.50 – 4.00, High Influence (HI) - 2.50 – 3.49, Moderate Influence (MI) - 1.50 – 2.49 and No Influence (NI) - 0.50 – 1.49. This real limit was applied to research questions. Conversely, in testing the null hypotheses at .05 level of significance, H_0 was rejected in favour of H_1 when the computed statistical value exceeded or was equal to the table value, otherwise, H_0 was retained.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the influence of control entry on job performance of public secondary schools teachers in Akwa Ibom State based on gender?

Table 1: Mean ratings of respondents on the influence of control entry on job performance of public secondary schools teachers in Akwa Ibom State based on gender n= 382

S/N	What is the influence of the following control entry items on teachers' job Performance?	Male			Female		
		\bar{X}	SD	Remark	\bar{X}	SD	Remark
1.	Ensuring that teachers without educational qualifications are not allowed to teach	2.99	0.63	High Influence	3.01	0.64	High Influence
2.	Ensuring that teachers pass through suitable selection exercises before they are appointed	2.70	1.15	High Influence	2.78	1.12	High Influence
3.	Ensuring that teachers are recruited based on merit	2.79	0.74	High Influence	2.80	0.76	High Influence
4.	Ensuring that only teachers who are registered with TRCN are allowed to teach.	2.67	0.85	High Influence	2.73	0.83	High Influence
5.	Conducting regular verification to fish out quacks.	3.20	0.80	High Influence	3.19	0.82	Moderate Extent
	Cluster Mean/SD	2.87	0.83	High Influence	2.90	0.83	High Influence

Table 1 shows the influence of control entry on the job performance of public secondary school teachers in Akwa Ibom State. All the items have their mean ratings within the range of 2.70 – 3.20, which indicates a high influence rating by all the respondents. On the whole, the cluster mean of 2.87 and 2.90 indicate that control entry has a high influence on the job performance of secondary schools teachers in Akwa Ibom State as rated by male and female respondents, respectively. The standard deviation range is low showing that the respondents were convergent in their opinions.

Research Question 2

What is the influence of code of conduct on the job performance of public secondary schools teachers in Akwa Ibom State based on years of service?

Table 2: Mean ratings of respondents on the influence of code of conduct on job performance of public secondary schools teachers in Akwa Ibom State based on years of service n= 382

S/N	What is the influence of the following code of conduct items on teachers' job Performance?	7-14 years			15 years/above		
		\bar{X}	SD	Remark	\bar{X}	SD	Remark
1.	Keeping students' records confidential	3.67	0.47	Very High Influence	3.67	0.47	Very High Influence
2.	Obedying established laws	2.25	0.60	Moderate Influence	2.41	0.55	Moderate Influence
3.	Being fair in the discharge of duties	3.39	0.58	High Influence	2.45	0.50	Moderate Influence
4.	Keeping to ethical standards in dealing with students	2.39	0.57	Moderate Influence	1.73	0.86	Moderate Influence
5.	Showing affective commitment in the discharge duties	2.22	0.76	Moderate Influence	2.18	0.79	Moderate Influence
	Cluster Mean/SD	2.78	0.60	High Influence	2.49	0.63	Moderate Influence

Table 2 shows the influence of code of conduct on the job performance of public secondary schools teachers in Akwa Ibom State based on years of service. All the items have their mean ratings within the range of 2.18 – 3.67 which indicates that code of conduct has a high influence on the job performance of teachers. On the whole, the cluster mean of 2.78 and 2.49 indicated that code of conduct has a high influence on the job performance of secondary schools teachers in Akwa Ibom State as rated by the respondents. The standard deviation range is low showing that the respondents were convergent in their opinions.

Research Question 3

What is the influence of training on the job performance of public secondary schools teachers in Akwa Ibom State based on qualifications?

Table 3: Mean ratings of respondents on the influence of training on job performance of public secondary schools teachers in Akwa Ibom State based on qualifications n=382

S/N	What is the influence of the following training items on teachers' job Performance?	NCE			B.Ed/above		
		\bar{X}	SD	Remark	\bar{X}	SD	Remark
1.	In-service training	3.64	0.48	Very High Influence	3.68	0.47	Very High Influence
2.	Workshop attendance	3.03	0.63	High Influence	3.42	0.61	High Influence
3.	Conference attendance	3.01	0.70	High Influence	2.83	0.78	High Influence
4.	Short courses attendance	2.57	0.66	High Influence	2.80	0.74	High Influence
5.	Orientation training	2.27	0.78	Moderate Influence	2.18	0.78	Moderate Influence
	Cluster Mean/SD	2.90	0.65	High Influence	2.98	0.67	High Influence

Table 3 shows the influence of training on the job performance of public secondary schools teachers in Akwa Ibom State based on qualifications. All the items have their mean range between 2.18 – 3.68 which indicates very high influence for Item 1, high influence for items 2, 3 and 4, while item 5 has moderate influence. On the whole, the cluster means of 2.90 and 2.98 indicated that training has a high influence on the job performance of secondary schools teachers in Akwa Ibom State as rated by NCE and B.Ed/BSc.Ed/B.A.Ed and above respondents. The standard deviation range is low showing that the respondents were convergent in their opinions

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleliv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 3, DECEMBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

*Nkeyemudim Emmanuel Essien
& Frank O. Udukeke*

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female teachers on the influence of control entry on their job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State.

Table 4: t-test analysis of the difference in the mean ratings of male and female teachers on the influence of control entry on their job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State

Gender	N	\bar{X}	SD	df	t-cal	t-critical	Decision
Male X_1	187	2.87	.83	380	0.88	1.96	NS
Female X_2	195	2.90	.83				

The result presented in table 4 shows that the calculated t-value of 0.88 is less than the t-critical value of 1.96 at .05 level of significance with a degree of freedom of 380. With this result, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of teachers on the influence of control entry on their job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State based on gender is therefore retained.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of teachers on the influence of code of conduct on their job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State based on years of service.

Table 5: t-test analysis of the difference in the mean ratings of teachers on the influence of code of conduct on their job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State based on years of service.

Years of service	N	\bar{X}	SD	df	t-cal	t-critical	Decision
7-14 years X_1	171	2.78	.60	380	1.79	1.96	NS
15 years/above X_2	211	2.49	.63				

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 3, DECEMBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

*Nkeyemudim Emmanuel Essien
& Frank O. Udukeke*

The result presented in table 5 shows that the calculated t-value of 1.79 is less than the t-critical value of 1.96 at .05 level of significance with the degree of freedom of 380. With this result, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of teachers on the influence of code of conduct on their job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State based on years of service is therefore retained.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of teachers on the influence of training on their job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State based on qualification.

Table 6: t-test analysis of the difference in the mean ratings of teachers on the influence of training on their job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State based on qualification

Qualifications	N	\bar{X}	SD	df	t-cal	t-critical	Decision
NCE X ₁	74	2.90	.65	380	1.52	1.96	NS
B.Ed/above X ₂	308	2.98	.67				

The result presented in table 6 shows that the calculated t-value of 1.52 is less than the t-critical value of 1.96 at .05 level of significance with the degree of freedom of 380. With this result, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of teachers on the influence of training on their job performance in public secondary schools based on qualifications is therefore retained.

Discussion of Findings

The result of research question one in table 1 revealed that control entry has a high influence on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State. This finding correlates with that of Jekayinfa (2013) who found that control entry has a positive relationship with teachers' job performance. The result of the study also

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 3, DECEMBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

*Nkeyemudim Emmanuel Essien
& Frank O. Udukeke*

revealed that control of entry is an important tool for teachers' job performance and effectiveness. Just like other professions, control entry helps to ensure that all teachers possess the requisite qualifications and knowledge before they are allowed into the teaching profession. The result of the null hypothesis one in table 4 showed that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of teachers on the influence of control entry on their job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State. This finding is in line with the finding of Igwegbuike and Ekwejuno-Etchie (2008) who found a significant relationship between control entry and teachers' job performance. When there is less or no control of entry into the teaching profession, it could lead to poor job performance.

The result of research question two in table 2 revealed that code of conduct has a high influence on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State. This finding correlates with the findings of Salahudina, Alwia, Siti Baharuddina and Halimata (2016) who found that work ethics and job performance are positively and significantly related. The result of the null hypothesis two in table 5 showed that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of teachers on the influence of code of conduct on their job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State. This finding is in line with the finding of Hasbullah and Moeins (n.d.) who discovered that professionalism, achievement motivation, empowerment and discipline at work significantly influence teachers' performance. To regulate the conduct of its accredited practitioners, professions usually have well-defined code of ethics. It is the code of ethics that constitutes the main yardstick for measuring the practitioners' standards of behaviour required in the profession. The code of ethics spells out inter and intra-group conducts. Such issues relating to personal relationships with other members of the profession, conduct with clients, and even employers are within the realm of the code of ethics for the teaching profession. It is assumed that the professional teacher is not only an individual who understands thoroughly his job, but one that can be trusted and as such would not manipulate his ignorant students or other stakeholders for the fulfillment of personal gains of any sort.

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 3, DECEMBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

*Nkeyemudim Emmanuel Essien
& Frank O. Udukeke*

The result of research question three in table 3 revealed that training has a high influence on the job performance of public secondary school teachers in Akwa Ibom State. This finding corroborates the finding of Akinyele (2017) who found that staff development has a positive relationship with job performance. The study showed that teachers who are exposed to development programmes such as seminars, workshops, educational conferences, symposia, among others, were more effective in their jobs. Similarly, the result of this study is in concord with the finding of Awan and Saeed (2014) who found a positive relationship between training and employees' performance. The result of the null hypothesis three in table 6 showed that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of teachers on the influence of training on their job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State. This finding is also in line with the finding of Jaoko (2014) whose study revealed that the level of training and academic qualification have a positive and significant relationship with job performance. However, the finding of this study is in contrast with the finding of Rashid (2008) whose study revealed that various training programmes that are available in the Federal College of Education, Zaria did not impact positively in enhancing the skills and knowledge of the staff and their performance. This difference may be due to the use of less-qualified trainers for such programmes. When teachers are exposed to quality training regularly, they will be more competent to carry out their assigned duties and responsibilities in the school system. Any profession demands a minimum duration of intense exposure to theoretical and practical knowledge to ensure an adequate understanding of the various aspects of that profession. It is only when a new entrant satisfies the requirements that he/she can be registered as a member of the profession. In other words, any profession has definite laid down procedures for its members to follow. No individual can be drafted into a professional practice without meeting the requirements of formal preparation.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it is concluded that non-adherence to professionalism criteria has made the teaching profession to be dominated by quacks who lack teaching skills, professional behaviour and knowledge required for effective job performance

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 3, DECEMBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

Nkeyemudim Emmanuel Essien
& Frank O. Udukeke

that could bring about desirable changes in students' academic performance. Quality graduates can only be churned out of the secondary school system when professionalism criteria are strictly adhered to.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. The State Ministry of Education and school administrators should ensure code of conduct are made available to teachers and are held accountable for any breach. This would ensure that teachers conduct themselves as expected.
2. The Akwa Ibom State Universal Basic Education Board and Teaching Service Commission should ensure that in the course of recruiting teachers for schools, only candidates who are professionally qualified are considered for employment for teaching.
3. The government should intensify efforts and put in place more appropriate training mechanisms such as symposia and seminars to avail teachers the opportunity to improve their performance and subsequently increase the general quality of education.

References

- Akinyele, S. T. (2017). The impact of Nigerian training programmes on employees' performance. *Research Journal of Business Management*, (1): 11-9.
- Akpan, A. E. (2004). *Fundamentals of entrepreneurship*. Ikot Ekpene: Brian Publishers (Nig) Ltd.
- Avery, A. (2013). *The System of the Professions*, Chicago: University of Chicago Press,
- Awata, B. B. (2012). *A Modern Sociology of Education: A Systematic Analysis*. Warri: COEWA Publishers.

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 3, DECEMBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

Nkeyemudim Emmanuel Essien
& Frank O. Udukeke

Awan, A. G. and Saeed, F. (2014). Impact of professional training on employees' performance: A Case study of Pakistani banking sector. *European Journal of Accounting Auditing and Finance Research*, 2(8): 70-80.

Dapper, F. H. (2014). The induction of probationer teachers: Implications of an industrial model. *Scottish Education Review*, 23(1): 23-31.

Dittimiya, I. A. (2008). *Introduction to Sociology of Education*, Warri: VOA Press

Emah, J. O. and Etuk, G. A. (2013). Developing teaching manpower in the new millennium through the distant learning system of the national teachers' institute in Nigeria, In J. B. Babalola; G. O. Akpan; A. O. A. Ayeni and S. O. Adedeji (Eds) *Access, Equity and Quality in Higher Education*. Awemark Industrial Printers Ltd, Ibadan

Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013). *The National Policy on Education*. 5th Edition, Lagos: NERDC Press

Hornby, A. S. (2010). *Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary*, 6th Edition, London: Oxford University Press.

Igwegbuike, M. R. and Ekwejuno, C. E. (2008). Liking of personal names, self-esteem, and the Big Five Inventory. *Psychological Reports*, 91: 407-410.

Jaoko, A. F. (2014). *Perceived Relationship between Employee Academic Qualifications and Job Performance in Mukuru Slums Development Projects, Nairobi County*. A published Masters Dissertation of University of Nairobi.

Jekayinfa, A. A. (2013). *Fundamentals of Principles and Practice of Instruction Textbook*, Ilorin: Bamitex Printing Press.

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 3, DECEMBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

Nkeyemudim Emmanuel Essien
& Frank O. Udukeke

- NOUN (2014). *Professionalism in Teaching*. Lecture note of School of Education, National Open University.
- Ogbodo C.M., Etuk, E. F. and Atangidel (2013). Financing education in Nigeria. In V. E. Peretomode (ed), *Introduction to Educational Administration, Planning and Supervision*, Ikeja: Joja Press Ltd.
- Oleforo, N. A. & Udukeke, F. O. (2018). Strategies for resolving and managing staff conflict by principals in public secondary schools in Nigeria. *Journal of Education*, 10(1), 253-260.
- Oleforo, N. A., Udukeke, F. O. & Abba, A. E. (2016). Forecasting skills needs and education students' reliance in Universities in Akwa Ibom State. *Education Journal*, 2(3), 114-122.
- Peretomode and Peretomode (2011). *Fundamentals of Management and Organisational Behaviour*, Benin City: Justice-Jeco Press.
- Rashid, F. (2015). *Mutual Accountability and Its Influence on Team Performance*. Doctoral Dissertation, Harvard University, Graduate School of Arts & Sciences.
- Salahudina, S. N., Alwi, M. N., Siti S. B., Baharuddin, S. and Halimat, S. B. (2016). *The Relationship between Work Ethics and Job Performance*. BE-ci 2016: 3rd International Conference on Business and Economics, 21–23. <http://dx.doi.org/10.15405/epsbs.2016.11.02.43>.
- Tedjere, S. R. (2011). *An introduction to Teacher Education in Nigeria*, Warri: COEWA Publishers.